

MOTIVATIONAL INCENTIVES AND THE PERFORMANCE OF ELECTRICITY SERVICES IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study evaluated the Motivational Incentives and the Performance of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives: Identify the relationship between profit sharing and efficiency; and determine the linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 2092 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 325, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was used. 297 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings include that there was positive significant relationship between profit sharing and efficiency ($r = 0.611 < 0.791, p < 0.05$). There was positive significant linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria as ($r = 0.530 < 0.739, p < 0.05$). The study concluded that engaged employees and payment of bonuses had positive significant relationship with profitability and volume of energy sold of electricity services in South East, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that Efficiency in the organization is available due to expertise and as such organizations that want to maximize their organizational efficiency should use the training and development method of motivation as it will help to develop the employees both in knowledge and in ability.

Keywords: Motivational, Incentives, Performance, Electricity, Services

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

As the environment changes, organizations try to adapt. They need to understand the importance of both working environments and extrinsic rewards. If one of them is missing, then employees will not be satisfied with their work and that dissatisfaction will lead to bad health and an increase in turnover. Organizations use various

strategies to retain employees and for that purpose, they have different policies in the organization that recognize the efforts of those employees (Asare, 2019). Generous and specific incentives can help drive and sustain a rapid performance improvement. Effectively motivating employees to achieve a desired outcome is one of the most important functions of a business manager. Business managers who can motivate employees assist the organization by improving employee retention and reinforcing positive behaviours and consequently, their enduring ability to effectively motivate workers to achieve the highest result determines the level of success of a business. Hugh, Robin & Dominic, (2022) asserts that supporting hundreds of transformation efforts, generous and specific incentives are one of the most effective tools available for managers to motivate employees. In fact, organizations that implemented incentives tied directly to transformation outcomes achieved almost a fivefold increase in total shareholder returns (TSR) compared with companies without similar programs. Organizational success depends on the collective efforts of the staff. The employees will collectively contribute to organizational growth when they are motivated (Susan, 2018) and Mbah, Ekechukwu & Chukwudi (2018)

Organizations must carefully consider these choices to achieve their desired behavioral changes and outcomes. Most of the time, organizations focus on giving financial rewards to their employees but they sometimes forget that non-financial rewards are also important to keep employees motivated toward work. Therefore, both incentives are important when trying to motivate employees and we need leaders to create an environment for the employees that enable them to feel motivated toward work (Anser, Yousaf, Majid & Yasir, 2020).

Motivation is the driver of guidance, control and persistence in human behavior. Increased motivation and discipline can be pursued by the provision of incentive. To motivate the employee in working can be done by giving a fair and reasonable incentive. Motivation refers to a process of inducing and stimulating an individual to act in certain manner (Byju's, 2023). In the context of an organisation, motivation implies encouraging and urging the employees to perform to the best of their capabilities so as to achieve the desired goals of the organisation. It refers to driving the individual psychologically so as to induce his willingness to work and perform better. In an organisation motivation can take various forms such as promotion, appraisal, recognition, etc. depending on the expectations and desires of the employee. Motivation implies encouraging and urging the employees to perform to the best of their capabilities so as to achieve the desired goals of the organisation. Motivation is a force which cause people to behavior particularly and according to management point of view, the aim of creating motivation in employees is to have a behavior in which brings the highest benefits for the organization. Motivational incentive is what drives people to perform, grow, and achieve their goals in therapy, coaching, or organizational settings. It plays a key role in determining a range of factors (Moore, 2021).

Performance is a function of the interaction between an individual's motivation, ability, and environment. Performance is assessed by managers daily and more formally in performance appraisal and development review. To secure performance, management must work on characteristics that can be changed (Timeless, 2023). Performance must be measured against job descriptions and goal set from time to time; and goals and expectations must be quantified. Fundamentally, organizational managers sense the presence of motivation by assessing the performance of a worker. But performance is not easy to measure. Motivation as a meaningful construct is a desire to satisfy a certain want and is a central pillar at the workplace. Thus, motivating employees adequately is a challenge as it has what it takes to define employee satisfaction at the workplace (Forson, Ofosu-Dwamena, Opoku & Adjavon, 2021). Motivation is not only one of the forces that lead to performance but also enhance performance.

1.2 Statement of the study

Most organizations form work teams to maximize employees' skills and strengths to improve performance. Motivation is one of the main functions of organizational management in the social sector. It can influence the success or organization negatively or positively depending on how it is being regarded in the organization, therefore it takes an important role. Motivators like promotions create a drive for employees to work to the best of their capabilities. As such, motivation in an organisation will lead to an increase in the productivity of an employee, who will contribute more compared to a disheartened employee.

Creating a system that can motivate all employees is not an easy task because these employees are all different people and unique in different ways. Various standards of living and cultures will result in unique motivation combinations which become a great challenge to managers. As such, the organization tends to suffer due to lack of knowledge on profit sharing and absence of bonus pay.

Motivation incites or induces the action of employees. A motivational system is meant to meet all the employees' needs. As soon as their satisfaction is fulfilled, the employees will tend to outline an independent relationship between their involuntary wish of performing the professional activity and their mood, hence, the problems of motivation shouldn't be avoided as it can lead to poor efficiency and volume of energy sold.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The main objectives of the study were to evaluate Motivational Incentives and the Performance of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives:

- i. Identify the relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria
- ii. Determine the linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. Identify the relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria
- ii. Determine the linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses guided the study

- i. There is no positive relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria
- ii. There is no positive linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

1.6 Significant of the study

The study will be beneficial to the employees and employers of every organization that aims to achieve its objective, increase performance and maximize profit. The study can also widen the researcher's knowledge on the different types of motivational incentives and the state in which each type is best applied.

Review of the related Literature

Conceptual review

2.1.1 Motivation

Motivation is "powering people to achieve high levels of performance and overcoming barriers in order to change. Motivation is the word derived from the word 'motive' which means needs, desires, wants or drives within the individuals (Juneja, 2022). It is the process of stimulating people to actions to accomplish the goals. Motivation is the psychological process that gets employees going, keeps them going, and determines the direction and strength of the effort they apply. It's what causes them to stop and apply their energies elsewhere. Motivation and performance lead to personal outcomes for each employee. When aggregated, employee outcomes lead to organisational outcomes like turnover and profit. If there's motivation, performance is possible (Timeless, 2023). Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behavior. It is often held that different mental states compete with each other and that only the strongest state determines behavior (Wasserman and Wasserman, 2020).

2.1.2 Incentives

Incentives is defined as variable rewards granted according to variations in the achievement of specific results. It is also called a stimulus to greater action. They may be used to incite action or greater effort. An incentive is anything which can be given in addition to wages. Incentives are therefore motivations for work (Ogohi & Cross, 2019). An incentive is a powerful tool to influence certain desired behaviors or action often adopted by governments and businesses. It is broadly divided into intrinsic and extrinsic incentives. Incentives are instrumental drive towards employee motivation and employee's productivity as it has great benefits and high potential to motivate workers to put in their best in any given task. Alfandi and Alkawsaneh, (2014) opined that by definition, incentives are an external persuading factor that encourages the motive which positively directs the individual into working harder, matching the required performance in the institution, as to get the incentive. Incentives are also defined both as methods used by institutions to encourage employees to work with high spirits and also as concrete and moral methods of satisfying the individuals' moral and material desires. Organizations must ensure they use the best incentives to get the required result from their employee's. Incentives are considered one of the most important factors that encourage workers to put forth great efforts and work more efficiently. It is because incentives and reward system direct workers capabilities into more efficiency in their work in an attempt to achieve the institution's goals. The idea of incentives triggers much consideration especially from the beginning of looking for qualified employees who are able to efficiently achieve the institution's goals. The importance of incentives originates from the need for the employee to be recognized and appreciated for his or her efforts (Alfandi and Alkawsaneh, 2014).

2.1.3 Motivational incentives

Motivational incentives lead to higher rates of retention in the organization. Motivational incentives are a type of reward system where someone where somehow an individual receives some type of motivation for their performance. Incentive programs are designed to attract, engage, and retain talent. Incentives themselves are rewards and benefits used to motivate positive behaviors in your workforce. They come in many forms, like tuition reimbursement, more time off, and additional flexibility in work arrangements (Wong, 2020). The more motivated the employees are, the more empowered the team is. Every concern requires physical, financial and human resources to accomplish the goals. It is through motivation that the human resources can be utilized by making full use of it. This can be done by building willingness in employees to work. This will help the enterprise in securing best possible utilization of resources.

2.1.3.1 Profit sharing

Profit sharing is an incentive plans introduced by organization that provide direct or indirect payments to employees depending on the organizations profitability in addition to employees' regular salary and bonuses. The profit sharing plans are based on predetermined economic sharing rules that define the split of gains between the company as a principal and the employee as an agent. Britannica, (2022) defined profit sharing, system as a system by which employees are paid a share of the net profits of the company that employs them, in accordance with a written formula defined in advance. Such payments, which may vary according to salary or wage, are distinct from and additional to regular earnings. Profit sharing differs from employee bonuses, which are usually given when a company sees a profit. Profit sharing can be an excellent way for employers to reward employees for their great performance. Profit-sharing plans can deliver a wide range of perks, starting with tax benefits. This allows businesses to minimize their tax liability and increase their savings (JMG, 2020). Before a profit-sharing plan can be implemented, a business must first complete Internal Revenue Service Form.

2.1.3.2 Payment of bonuses

A bonus is a financial compensation that is above and beyond the normal payment expectations of its recipient. Bonuses may be awarded by a company as an incentive or to reward good performance. Bonus pay is compensation in addition to the amount of pay specified as a base salary or hourly rate of pay. Bonus pay is also an additional pay given to an employee on top of their regular earnings; it's used by many organizations as a thank-you to employees or a team that achieves significant goals. Bonus pay is also offered to improve employee morale, motivation, and productivity (Heathfield, 2020). When a company ties bonuses to performance, it can encourage employees to reach their goals, which in turn helps the company reach its goals.

The ultimate goal of handing out bonuses is to make employees feel valued, increasing productivity and in doing so, create a positive environment for the achievement of organisation goals. Bonuses are a type of compensation paid to an eligible employee in addition to a previously set hourly wage, contract amount or annual salary. While many companies provide bonuses in the form of cash, a bonus can take any form as long as it provides value to employees as well as the organization (Herrit, 2023).

2.1.4 Performance

Performance comprises the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs. Performance can be subjective depending on the organization, its goals and the market. Performance is the ability of an organization to reach its goals and optimize results. In today's workforce, organizational performance can be defined as a company's ability to achieve goals in a state of constant change (Miles, 2022). Organizational performance is also the success or fulfillment of organization at the end of program or projects as it is intended. Employee performance fundamentally depends on many factors like performance appraisals, employee motivation, employee satisfaction, compensation, training and development, job security, organizational structure e.t.c. performance in an organization is the success or fulfillment of organization at the end of program or projects as it is intended. Tahir, (2020) noted that organizational performance is a ubiquitous term which is nevertheless loosely defined. Though the construct depends on a number of unique factors associated with each organization, yet the lack of a universal definition makes it challenging for professionals to concur about what exactly they mean by organizational performance.

2.1.4.1 Efficiency

The term "efficiency" refers to the peak level of performance that uses the least amount of inputs to achieve the highest amount of output. It can also be defined as the ability to achieve an end goal with little to no waste, effort, or energy (Banton, Boyle and Schmitt, 2022). It requires reducing the number of unnecessary resources used to produce a given output, including personal time and energy. Efficiency occurs when there is reduce in waste to produce a given number of goods or services. Business efficiency describes how effectively a company generates products and services related to the amount of time and money needed to produce them. Efficient companies make the most of their resources, transforming labor, materials and capital into products and services that create profit for the company. Inefficient companies, on the other hand, lack organization, which can slow down their operations, waste time and money and impact profitability (Jenkins, 2022).

2.1.4.2 Volume of energy sold

Energy is the strength and vitality required for sustained physical or mental activity. Energy sold is the sale of energy by the Company or its Subsidiaries. The word energy derives from the Ancient Greek: ἐνέργεια, Romanized: energeia, lit. 'activity, operation', which possibly appears for the first time in the work of Aristotle in the 4th century BC. In contrast to the modern definition, energeia was a qualitative philosophical concept, broad enough to include ideas such as happiness and pleasure (Harper, 2007). Electrical energy is the energy derived from electric potential energy or kinetic energy of the charged particles. In general, it is referred to as the energy that has been converted from electric potential energy. Electrical energy can be generated by the movement of electrons from one point to another. The movement of charged particles along/through a medium (say wire) constitutes current or electricity.

2.1.5 Electricity services

Electric service means the furnishing of electric power and energy for lighting, heating, power, or any other purpose for which electric power and energy can be used. Electric service is the firm energy associated with the allocation and sold by the Authority to the customer in accordance with this agreement, service. Law, (n.d) defined electric service as the supply of electricity including generation, transmission, distribution and ancillary services for ultimate consumption. Electricity services implies the services related to the arrangement of electricity to an individual, including the trading of electric energy, making monetary game plans to oversee economic danger associated with the pool value distribution access service, framework access, administration, subordinate services, charging, metering, performing load repayment and some other services determined in guidelines made under Act (Quora, 2023).

2.1.6 Conceptual Framework of the study

2.2 Theoretical Framework of the study

Organismic theory of motivation (OTM) is a sub theory of Self-determination Theory. Authors Deci and Ryan created the theory to introduce different forms of extrinsic motivation and the contextual factors that either promote or prevent internalization or integration of the regulation for these behaviors (Deci & Ryan 72, 1985). Organismic theory states that contextual help for autonomy, completeness and relatedness contributes internalization and integration. The theory further states that human beings are guided by a sovereign drive for self-actualization or self-realization. This observation led to the more general theory that any event whatever, either psychological or physiological, occurs within the context of the total organism and must be viewed in a holistic light. In other words, persons prefer more to internalize and integrate value, experience choice with respect to it and connection with those who provide it. According to SDT, the more autonomous motivation is the more perseverance and productivity employees show. (Wellbeing in Developing Countries, 2009).

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 The relationship between profit sharing and efficiency

Zakkia and Asim (2021) conducted a study on the Impact of Non-Financial Rewards on Employees Motivation in Banking Sector of Peshawar, Pakistan. This paper shows to measure the impact of non-financial rewards on the motivation of employees in different banks of Pakistan. The purpose of this paper is to know the impact of the non-financial rewards on employee's motivation and will classify to what extent the HR are taking care of this source of employee motivation. The paper follows an empirical study and quantitative approach. For non-financial rewards, there are five independent variables taken for this study; rewards & recognition, career opportunity, promotion, participation of employees in decision-making and responsibility to identify their impact on the employee's motivation. For effective collection of primary data from the target respondents, a Likert scaled questionnaire used, and 185 employees are taken from seven different banks in, Peshawar Pakistan. SPSS used to evaluate all of the data in order to find and measure the spearman association among the dependent and independent variables. All the data presented using tables. All non-financial reward variables found to have a significant association in the analysis.

Upathissa (2022) carried out a study on an Empirical Study of the Factors Effecting Motivation and their Effectiveness on Employee Performance. The study is on the factors of motivation and their effectiveness on employee performance. And it is emphasized on the non-managerial staff of the tea factories in Pelmadulla divisional secretariat in Ratnapura district. The main objective of this analysis is to identify the factors of motivation and their effectiveness in employee performances. Employee performance is a vital factor in achieving organizational goals as well industrial goals. In the introduction, it explained the identified problem of lack of motivation among employees in the tea factories. According to that most of the workers are very stressed with the job environment and less morale among them. The present study carries out a detailed analysis on identified motivation factors in the literature. Thereby motivation theories and the concept of employee performance were also reviewed. A field survey with questionnaires for non-managerial staff is conducted by using simple random sampling and snowball sampling method. Further conducted interviews with employees, tea factory managers, factory owners to identify and collect data on the present status of employee performance.

Eleje (2022) conducted a study on the Effect of Reward System on Productivity and Efficiency of Employees of University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Enugu State, South-east Nigeria. The study examined effect of reward system on productivity and efficiency of employees of University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital

(UNTH), Enugu. The main objectives are focused on the effect of training and development and fringe benefits as reward system on workers' productivity and efficiency in University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Enugu. The study adopted the equity theory to explain how reward system affects productivity and efficiency. It also adopted descriptive survey research design. Simple random sampling was used to select a total of 706 employees from a population of 2,216. For collection of data from the respondents a set of questionnaire that consisted of close-ended items set on 5- point Likert-type scale was used. Data from the questionnaire was analyzed by descriptive statistics aided by SPSS and presented in tables using frequencies, percentage, mean score and standard deviation, while the hypotheses was tested by inferential statistics known as multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study show that among others that effective use of various forms of training and development as reward system are found to have effect on employees' productivity and efficiency on the job at the University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital (UNTH), Enugu. It was also discovered that various forms of fringe benefits used as reward to a high extent enhanced productivity and among employees. It was found that fringe benefits in this instance served as incentives that motivated efficient performance among employees. The study concludes that effective rewards system such as may fall under training and development are found to enhance employees' productivity on the job.

Rajesh, Pratima, Ramesh, Shobha and Nidhi (2022) conducted a study on Enhancing Employee Performance through Monetary Incentives - A Thematic Analysis. Thematic analysis of the role of monetary incentives to enhance employee performance is described critically in this particular study paper. This report clarifies the aim of this research paper to understand about monetary incentive system in the area of the competitive business market, the major responsibilities of the incentive process enhancing the power of employee performance, the process to increase business productivity through financial rewards, and important tool or process to analysis positive effect of employee incentive method in the business market, authentic data and information to relate with business improvement through the effect of monetary incentive process and finding future scope or more opportunities to provide a safe platform for the employee. This analysis study focuses on all those areas to clarify importance to provide employee incentives to achieve the best performance as well as business productivity.

Uzochukwu, Nwankwo and Okafor (2023) carried out a study on the Effect of reward system on employee's productivity in Nigeria hospitality industry. This study investigated the effect of reward system on employee productivity in Nigeria hospitality industry. The specific objectives of the study are to: assess the effect of sizeable wage and salary reward system on employee quality of service delivery in Nigeria hospitality industry and ascertain the effect of retirement benefits reward system on employee commitment in Nigeria hospitality industry. Research design was descriptive survey research. Study Area was Enugu State. Sample size of 378 respondents was drawn from 503 population of the study using Taro Yamane sample technique. The research question was answered with simple percentage, mean and deviation while methods of data presentation are table and simple percentage. The hypotheses were tested with regression analysis comprising student-t statistics. The following are the major findings of the study: the study revealed that sizeable wage and salary reward system has significant effect on employee quality of service delivery in hospitality industry (t -statistics (8.312) > P-value (0.000); the study reveals that retirement benefits reward system has significant effect on employee commitment in hospitality industry (t -statistics (9.491) > P-value (0.000). The study concludes that there was positive and significant effect of reward system on employee productivity in hospitality industry especially in Nike Lake Resort Hotel Enugu Nigeria.

2.3.2 The linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity services in South East, Nigeria.

Ede, and Mbah, (2020), conducted a study on the evaluation of the relationship between organizational compensation and employee output in five selected manufacturing firms in south-east, Nigeria. The population for the study was five thousand, and eleven employees (5,011). The study sample size was eight hundred and ninety-five (895) respondents. Questionnaire which was validated by experts was the instrument used for data collection. Some of the major findings is that there is a positive relationship between access to training and employee product quality in the five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria ($r = .780$; $p = .000 > 0.05$, $n=895$); there is a positive relationship between organizational compensation and employees output in the five selected manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria ($r = .840$; $p = .000 > 0.05$, $n=895$). The study concluded that that if employees are well compensated and well trained, it will encourage more productivity and overall output. Consequent upon the findings, some recommendations were made; It is recommended that employees should be given access to continual training of all types just to keep up, firms should invest resources in training and coaching employees, which will, in turn, give their employees a sense of ethical obligation to respond with increased effort, and a desire to stay with the organization to 'repay the debt, Finally, firms should strategically structure their compensation plan accordingly. This can be done informally by asking employees with other companies that you interview about their compensation plan, or more objectively by hiring an outside consulting firm to benchmark their plan against others and advise you on how to adjust it.

Obiozor and Obiora (2021) conducted a study on the Influence of Cataloguers' Motivation on their Job Performances in Public University Libraries in South East Nigeria. The purpose of this paper is to examine the influence of cataloguers' motivation on their job performances in public university libraries in South East Nigeria. The study adopted both descriptive and correlational research design. This study was carried out in the South-East zone of Nigeria. It comprises Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. This area was chosen for the study in view of the fact that the region is well acclaimed as having educational advantage in Nigeria. The population of this study is 157, comprises all the catalogue librarians (professionals and paraprofessionals). The study employed three instruments to elicit data from the respondents. The questionnaires entitled: "Cataloguers' Job Performance Questionnaire" (CJPQ) and "Cataloguers' Motivation Questionnaire (CMQ). The Cataloguers' Job Performance Questionnaire (CJPQ) was adopted from Williams and Anderson (1991), and Halim and Sefer (2013) Task Performance Scales. The Cataloguers' Motivation Questionnaire (CMQ) was adapted from Halim and Sefer (2013) motivation scale and modified by the researcher. Data obtained from the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Percentages, mean and bar chart were used to analyze data. The findings of the study among others reveals that cataloguers were more "efficient" in their job performance, followed by their "effectiveness" to their job performance, and then their "learning and improvement". It was agreed that the cataloguers felt well motivated, while the relationship between cataloguers' motivation and their job performance is moderate and positive.

Olamilekan (2021) conducted a study on the Relevance of Financial Incentives on Employee Motivation in Nigeria. In capturing the relevance of financial incentives on employee motivation in Nigeria this paper is using GT bank as a case study. A primary form of data collection was employed where raw information was gathered via questionnaire and codified in numerical form for statistical analysis. Meanwhile, more than 230 questionnaires were distributed to the participants, though 230 questionnaires were validly filled. Correlation and regression

analyses were used and reported that pay and allowance exhibits a negative and insignificant impact on employee motivation, bonus incentives can influence employee motivation positively and significantly, promotion incentives contribute positively and significantly to employee motivation, and retirement benefits could impact employee motivation positively and significantly. It was concluded that a weak positive connection exists between employee motivation and pay and allowance, weak positive and significant connection exists between employee and bonus incentives, weak positive correlation and significant connection exists between the variables, and weak positive and significant correlation between employee motivation and retirement benefits.

Idigo, (2023) conducted a study on Incentives and Performance of Workers in Tertiary Institutions in Anambra and Enugu State, Nigeria. The main aim of this study is to investigate the incentives and performance of workers in tertiary institutions in Anambra and Enugu state, Nigeria. The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of monetary incentives, non-monetary incentives and career development on performance workers in tertiary institutions in Anambra and Enugu State. Relevant conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature was reviewed taking cognizance of the problem and the hypotheses of the study. The study is anchored on expectancy theory of work motivation. Descriptive research survey was adopted in this study. The population of the study were comprises of 7,300 selected academic and non-academic staff of the of the tertiary institutions in Anambra and Enugu state, Nigeria, while the sample size of 362 was obtain using connivance Sampling Technique of Nwana's (1992). Data was source from primary sources. The instrument was validated through face and content validity and research experts while internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha was used in test the reliability of the instrument used. Multiple regression analysis was employed in analyze the data generated. It was discovered that monetary incentives have a positive significant influence workers' productivity in Nigerian organization; Non- monetary incentives have a positive significant influence workers' productivity in Nigerian organization; while career development has negative significant effect on workers' productivity in Nigerian organization. The study concludes that incentives have a positive significant effect on workers' performance in Nigerian organization.

Shahzad, Khan, Iqbal, and Shabbir (2023) conducted a study on the Effects of Motivational and Behavioral Factors on Job Productivity: An Empirical Investigation from Academic Librarians in Pakistan. The major objective of the current study was to find out the impact of motivational factors on the job outcomes of librarians working in HEC-recognized university libraries in Pakistan. A survey research method followed by predictive correlational design was applied to test the constructed hypotheses in this study. The population of the study was library professionals working in the university libraries of Lahore, Pakistan. There were 13 public sector universities and 21 private sector universities. The census sampling technique was used to collect data from the respondents of the 34 universities. Data were collected with the help of a questionnaire. Out of 225 respondents, 189 completed questionnaires were received. Hence, the response rate was 84%. The gathered data were analyzed through SPSS software. Descriptive and inferential statistical tests were applied to find out the impact of motivational and behavioral factors on the job outcomes of information professionals. The findings of the study showed that different types of motivation influenced information professionals to carry out innovative and value-added services in the workplace.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The area of the study comprised staff of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population

of 2092 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 325, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error. 297 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 92 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.86 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) statistics tool.

4.0 Data Presentation and Analyses

4.1 Data relating to research question

4.1.1 The relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.1.1.1: Responses on The relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Giving employees a sense of ownership in the organization encourages them to put in their best.	655 131 44.1	320 80 26.9	48 16 5.4	58 29 9.8	41 41 13. 8	1122 297 100%	3.77	1.444	Agree
2	Aligning business success with employee success increases staff efficiency.	540 108 36.4	320 80 26.9	75 25 8.4	36 18 6.1	66 66 22. 2	1037 297 100%	3.49	1.562	Agree
3	Creating innovate solutions to problems were motivated by profit sharing.	560 112 37.7	396 99 33.3	78 26 8.8	40 20 6.7	40 40 13. 5	1114 297 100%	3.75	1.375	Agree
4	Profit sharing aid attract and retain top talent employees.	630 126 42.4	364 91 30.6	21 7 2.4	84 42 14. 1	31 31 10. 4	1130 297 100%	3.80	1.386	Agree
5	Effective cordial relations are enhanced in the oeganisation through profit sharing	600 120 40.4	364 91 30.6	54 18 6.1	40 20 6.7	48 48 16. 2	1106 297 100%	3.72	1.456	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.70	1.444	
								6	6	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1.1, 211 respondents out of 297 representing 71.0 percent agreed that giving employees a sense of ownership in the organization encourages them to put in their best with mean score 3.77 and standard deviation of 1.330. Aligning business success with employee success increases staff efficiency 188 respondents representing 63.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.49 and standard deviation of 1.425. Creating innovate

solutions to problems were motivated by profit sharing 211 respondents representing 71.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.75 and standard deviation of 1.245. Profit sharing aid attract and retain top talent employees 217 respondents representing 73.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.80 and 1.279. Effective cordial relations are enhanced in the oeganisation through profit sharing 211 respondents representing 71.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation 1.391.

4.2.2. The relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.2.1.1: Responses on the relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	Σ FX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	The organization has a gesture of appreciation towards their employees with bonus.	575 115 38.7	464 116 39.1	21 7 2.4	88 44 14. 8	15 15 5.1	1163 297 100%	3.92	1.207	Agree
2	Staff not only receives bonus for job well done but also to keep them motivated and focused in the business.	480 96 32.3	464 116 39.1	3 1 .3	76 38 12. 8 5	46 46 15.	1069 297 100%	3.60	1.442	Agree
3	Payment for bonus retains staff and increase energy to attract customers.	520 104 35.0	472 118 39.7	18 6 2.0	80 40 13. 5	29 29 9.8	1119 297 100%	3.77	1.319	Agree
4	The bonus gesture shows that the organization values and acknowledges good work.	560 112 37.7	376 94 31.6	69 23 7.7	12 6 2.0 9	62 62 20.	1079 297 100%	3.63	1.512	Agree
5	Addition to their base salary as part of their wages or salary facilities energy sales.	675 135 45.5	308 77 25.9	42 14 4.7	86 43 14. 5	28 28 9.4	1139 297 100%	3.84	1.381	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.75	1.372	
								2	2	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.2.1, 231 respondents out of 297 representing 77.8 percent agreed that the organization has a gesture of appreciation towards their employees with bonus with mean score 3.92 and standard deviation of 1.330. Staff not only receives bonus for job well done but also to keep them motivated and focused in the business 112 respondents representing 71.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.60 and standard deviation of 1.425. Payment for bonus retains staff and increase energy to attract customers 222 respondents representing 74.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.77 and standard deviation of 1.245. The bonus gesture shows that the organization values and acknowledges good work 206 respondents representing 69.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.63 and 1.279.

Addition to their base salary as part of their wages or salary facilities energy sales 212 respondents representing 71.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.84 and standard deviation 1.391.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 There is no positive relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.2.1 Pearson correlation of there is no positive relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria Correlations

		Giving employees a sense of ownership in the organization encourages them to put in their best.	Aligning business success with employee success increases staff efficiency.	Creating innovate solutions to problems were motivated by profit sharing.	Profit sharing aid attract and retain top talent employees.	Effective cordial relations are enhanced in the oeganisatio n through profit sharing
Giving employees a sense of ownership in the organization encourages them to put in their best.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 297	.711** .000 297	.692** .000 297	.611** .000 297	.628** .000 297
Aligning business success with employee success increases staff efficiency.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.711** .000 297	1 .000 297	.620** .000 297	.509** .000 297	.507** .000 297
Creating innovate solutions to problems were motivated by profit sharing.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.692** .000 297	.620** .000 297	1 .000 297	.616** .000 297	.791** .000 297

Profit sharing aid attract and retain top talent employees.	Pearson Correlation	.611**	.509**	.616**	1	.680**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	297	297	297	297	297
Effective cordial relations are enhanced in the oeganisation through profit sharing	Pearson Correlation	.628**	.507**	.791**	.680**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	297	297	297	297	297

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.2.1 showed the pearson correlation matrix on profit sharing and efficiency showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.611 < .791$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.00 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria ($r = .611 < .791$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = 611 < .791, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .611 < .791$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria ($r = .611 < .791$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = 611 < .791, p < .05$).

4.2.2 There is no positive linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.2.2 Pearson correlation of there is no positive linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria

Correlations

		The organization has a gesture of appreciation towards their employees with bonus.	Staff not only receives bonus for job well done but also to keep them motivated and focused in the business.	Payment for bonus retains staff and increase energy to attract customers.	The bonus gesture shows that the organization values and acknowledges good work.	Addition to their base salary as part of their wages or salary facilities energy sales.
The organization has a gesture of appreciation towards their employees with bonus.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .740** .000 297	.740** .000 297	.739** .000 297	.607** .000 297	.610** .000 297
Staff not only receives bonus for job well done but also to keep them motivated and focused in the business.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.740** .000 297	1 .000 297	.756** .000 297	.619** .000 297	.620** .000 297
Payment for bonus retains staff and increase energy to attract customers.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.739** .000 297	.756** .000 297	1 .000 297	.616** .000 297	.596** .000 297
The bonus gesture shows that the organization values and acknowledges good work.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.607** .000 297	.619** .000 297	.616** .000 297	1 .000 297	.530** .000 297
Addition to their base salary as part of their	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.610** .000 297	.620** .000 297	.596** .000 297	.530** .000 297	1 .000 297

wages or salary facilities energy sales.	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
N		297	297	297	297	297

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.2.2 showed the pearson correlation matrix on payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.530 < .739$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.00 level (2 tailed) and implies that there was positive significant linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria ($r = .530 < .739$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .530 < .739, p < .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .530 < .739$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that there was positive significant linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria ($r = .530 < .739$) as reported in the probability value of ($r = .530 < .739, p < .05$).

5.0 Summary of findings

The findings of the study showed that

- i. There was positive significant relationship between profit sharing and efficiency of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria ($r = .611 < .791, p < .05$).
- ii. There was positive significant linkage between payment of bonuses and raises on volume of energy sold of Electricity Services in South East, Nigeria as ($r = .530 < .739, p < .05$).

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that engaged employees and payment of bonuses had positive significant relationship with profitability and volume of energy sold of electricity services in South East, Nigeria. This implies that when employee performances are recognized and rewarded in the organization, they tend to perform better. The result of this study also showed that employees can also be motivated through monetary and non monetary aspect. Employee motivation drives the quality of work and boosts performance in an organization. When organizations keep their employees motivated, production can be done without interruption.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. Efficiency in the organization is available due to expertise and as such organizations that want to maximize their organizational efficiency should use the training and development method of motivation as it will help to develop the employees both in knowledge and in ability.
- ii. Organization should not only be interested in increasing its profit without recognizing its employees. Most a times the management tries to motivate the employees (poorly) in other to claim that it

motivates its employee whereas it's nothing compared to the performance of the employees. Thus, employee motivation should be in commensurate to their dedication to the work.

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